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SERVICE QUALITY OF BUS RAPID TRANSIT (BRT) ALONG THE IKORODU CORRIDORS, LAGOS STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Public transportation (PT) is important in urban areas for the movement of people and helps create a sustainable transport system in most cities. In 2008, the Lagos State Government, in collaboration with the World Bank, established a bus rapid transit (BRT) system of PT to address the lingering problem of chaotic, uncoordinated, and unreliable public transportation in the Lagos metropolis. The BRT system seems to offer higher service quality than the traditional buses in the metropolis. It attracts a mammoth crowd of commuters, including car owners, along its corridors. However, there are concerns by commuters over the deterioration in the service quality of the buses. It is on this note that this paper attempts to examine the transport system using the Ikorodu-CMS corridor as a case study using the SERVQUAL model to evaluate the service quality of the BRT services along the five dimensions of the model, namely, tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. Data was collected from a valid sample of 545 respondents from both Ikorodu and Agric BRT Bus terminals. The analysis of data showed that Lagos-BRT service quality is below the expectations of several commuters. The results indicated that the service quality of the buses along the four of the five dimensions fell below the expectations of commuters, making them perceive the quality as significantly low. The buses' unreliability contributed immensely to the perception of the buses' low service quality. Understanding commuters' perception of the service quality of Lagos BRT will enable both the bus operator, Primerio Bus Services, and the regulator, LAMATA, to monitor, review and improve the service quality of the buses and make the buses attractive to all categories of commuters in the state.

Keywords: Automobiles, BRT, commuters, public transportation, and service quality.

Introduction

One of the major challenges of the growing urbanization in both developing and developed countries is transportation (Imre & Celebi, 2017). The fast pace of urban population growth combined with rising automobile ownership and usage have created urban transportation problems in developing countries (Javid, Toshiyuki, Fumihiko, & Rui, 2013). Transportation challenges in Nigeria may be more pronounced due to rising population, bad leadership, corruption, and limited financial

and other resources needed to develop and maintain transportation equipment, infrastructure, and facilities. Despite the challenges of transportation, it remains a catalyst for human mobility. Eboli and Mazzulla (2012) observed that the mobility demand of people has increased steadily due to their desire to engage in socio-economic activities. Therefore, it has been claimed that transportation plays a crucial role in moving people and goods around and helps in sustaining economic activity (Transport Cooperative Research Programme, TCRP, 2011). While the masses depend on public transport (PT) for their commuting needs, few vehicle owners can commute either in private mode or in PT (Aminu & Pearse, 2018).

In the last few decades, urban areas around the world have become more automobile-dependent and less sustainable (Pojani & Stead, 2015). A majority of people owning automobiles, in most major cities across the world, make trips in their automobiles, thus causing problems for the people, the environment, and the infrastructure (Aminu, 2016). These problems include excessive fuel consumption, congestion, pollution, and health hazards (Aminu & Olayinka, 2014; Aminu & Pearse, 2018; Beirao & Cabral, 2006; Eboli & Mazzulla, 2007, 2012; Lagos Metropolitan Area Transport Authorities, LAMATA, 2013; Okanlawon, 2007).

The growing global incidence of automobile use suggests that PT may be losing its attractiveness and modal share. This is despite its importance in achieving sustainability, efficient mobility, and enhancing the quality of life of people in urban areas (Wardman & Waters, 2001).

In developing countries, the ridership of PT is common among the masses (Basorun & Rotowa, 2012). Due to its megacity status, a substantial number of commuters in Lagos State depend on buses of different sizes; motorcycles, popularly called "Okada"; Tricycles, commonly known as "Keke Marwa"; taxis; and walking. Due to its capacity, PT modes such as BRT, mass transit buses, coastal buses, and yellow mini-busses, known as "Danfo" accounts for a significant share of the total commuters in the state. This is the same situation in London (UK), where "buses are by far the most used mode of PT due to its flexibility, high availability, and accessibility" (Md Rohani, Wijeyesekera, & Abd. Karim, 2013) and in Johannesburg, South Africa where a large number of people depends on PT for their daily commuting (Govender, 2014).

Before the introduction of the BRT system of PT in Lagos State in 2008 (LAMATA, 2009), the World Bank (2012) aptly described the PT system in the state as chaotic, unreliable, and uncoordinated. The experience of many commuters, before the advent of the BRT system in Lagos State, was horrendous. They were roughly handled by rickety buses, abused by saucy conductors, and killed or crippled by reckless drivers and motorcycle riders (Bakare, 2016). This dreadful experience has made most automobile drivers result to regular driving and non-drivers consider buying a car (Aminu & Pearse, 2018). In collaboration with the World Bank, the Lagos State Government established a BRT system of PT in the Lagos metropolis on March 17,

2008, to create a safe, reliable, and integrated mass transit system (World Bank, 2012). BRT is a transport option that uses dedicated, interference-free segregated lanes to achieve fast and reliable journey (LAMATA, 2016). One of the unique features of the BRT system that makes it attractive to commuters is the dedicated, interference-free and segregated lanes (Aminu, 2014). In terms of patronage, Lagos BRT is similar to the BRT system in Curitiba, Brazil (Mobereola, 2009). For example, the number of commuters riding daily in Lagos BRT grew significantly from 180, 000 in 2013 to 260,000 in 2015 (LAMATA, 2016).

Due to the positive impact of the BRT system on Lagos residents and the redefinition of PT in the Lagos metropolis (Aminu & Pearse, 2018), the BRT system has attracted different categories of commuters. According to LAMATA (2009), these include 85% of the passengers who hitherto commuted in 'danfo'; 8% who previously commuted in the larger 'molue' (commercial buses); 4% that previously traveled by car; and an additional 2% meeting their commuting needs by Taxi, 'Okada' (commercial motorcycles) and 'Kabu Kabu' (commercial vehicles not painted in the government approved colours). Therefore, PT ridership has risen in Nigeria (LAMATA, 2009; Odufuwa, 2011; World Bank, 2012).

The BRT scheme is conceived to improve the level of service of bus-oriented mass transit options (Rodriguez & Targa, 2004). However, there are concerns about the declining service quality and capacity of Lagos BRT. Studies have suggested that transit services, quality, and capacity are generally very low in Nigeria (Adebambo & Adebayo, 2009; World Bank, 2012). In particular, commuters of BRT in the Lagos metropolis are groaning under the long waiting time to board buses at Ikorodu and other terminals in the state (Adeyeye, 2018), suggesting that the buses are not reliable. Bus shortage has caused untold pain for the commuters while BRT personnel are indifferent to their plight when they seek information from them (Igomu, 2018), suggesting that the BRT personnel are not responsive to the commuters' plights. For example, the number of buses, under the scheme, has shrunk from 434 to 250 (Proshare, 2018), suggesting that the buses are poorly maintained by the bus operators and poorly regulated by LAMATA.

In light of the foregoing, it is pertinent to evaluate the service quality of Lagos BRT. Service quality measures the degree to which the service delivered meets the customers' expectations (Yarimoglu, 2014). We measured the perception of the BRT buses along the five dimensions of the SERVQUAL model: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy (Parasuraman, Berry, & Zeithaml, 1988). SERVQUAL is a 21-item scale that has been widely used to evaluate service quality in the service industry. To achieve this objective, the following research question would be answered: What is the commuters' perception of Lagos BRT? While the research on PT in Nigeria is growing, there is dearth of research that has evaluated BRT service quality using these dimensions. More so, many of the extant studies in this area have been undertaken in western countries. This paper fills this gap in the literature by

providing pioneer evidence of BRT service quality in the Lagos metropolis. Understanding commuters' perception of the service quality of Lagos BRT will enable both the bus operator, Primerio Bus Services, and the regulator, LAMATA, to monitor, review, and improve the service quality of the buses and make the buses attractive to all categories of commuters. It is suggested that by offering quality services, companies can maintain customers' loyalty and competitive edges in the market (El Saghier, 2015).

The rest of the paper is structured into the following sections. Section two reviews extant literature; section three outlines the methods for collecting and analyzing data for the study; section four presents results; and finally, concluding remarks are made.

Perspectives on Public Transportation and Bus Rapid Transit

PT referred to all modes of transportation available to the public irrespective of who owns it (White, 2002). It is transportation by conveyance that continuously satisfy the general or special transportation needs of the public, excluding school buses, charter, and sightseeing services (Tran & Kleiner, 2005). It is the use of shared, and often state-operated or contracted, bus, ferry, tram, and train transport available for use by the general public including tourists to move around an area, excluding transport on city tour buses (Le-Klahn & Hall, 2015).

From these definitions, it can be seen that PT or mass transit mode, unlike automobiles, is available to everyone, including those who have no automobile and those who have automobiles but choose not to travel in their automobiles. PT mode provides the opportunity for commuting on a sharing basis and it may help to reduce the number of automobiles on the road if the service quality is appropriate. It can also reduce fuel consumption, reduce the amount of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and promotes a sustainable transport system in congested cities, like Lagos State. The dearth of public transport systems in developing countries can create acute externalities, such as traffic congestion, social exclusion, environmental degradation, and so on (Al-Rashid, Goh, Harumain, Ali, Campisi, & Mahmood, 2021).

Aminu and Olayinka (2014) explained that PT is a shared mode that can move a few people (e.g. taxis) or a large number of people (e.g. mass transport or railway) of different socio-economic strata, thus increasing the average occupancy rate of the mode. PT provides mobility to those who cannot or prefer not to drive, enabling them to access jobs, education, and medical services (Ferris, 2011). The use of PT mitigates the problem of unrestrained use of automobiles (Damayanto, Kenedi, & Yogatama, 2018) and promotes sustainability (Aminu & Pearse, 2018; Pojani & Stead, 2015). Examples of PT modes are taxis, coaches, private hired vehicles, buses, BRT, heavy rail transit, light rail transit, trolleys, and ferry boats (Aminu & Pearse, 2018; Balcombe et al., 2004; Gesellschaft fur Technische Zusammenarbeit (GTZ), 2003; Tran & Kleiner, 2005).

PT modes like bus services may not necessarily be commercially viable but they fulfill a social need of the community (Md Rohani et al., 2013). The low viability of bus services explains why governments, at both state and local levels in both developed and developing countries, invest in PT equipment, facilities, and infrastructure and provide affordable PT systems. Felleson and Friman (2008) affirmed that many countries have increased spending on the PT system to make it compete with other modes of transport, especially automobiles. In Lagos State, the Lagos State Government has made a huge investment, especially in the area of rehabilitation of road infrastructure and in the provision of buses and passengers supported facilities to make PT attractive in the state.

Many cities have developed variations on the theme of better bus services (GTZ, 2003). One of these variations is BRT. BRT is a category of buses and is a form of customer-orientated transit combining stations, vehicles, planning, and intelligent transport system elements into an integrated system with a unique identity (; Aminu & Pearse, 2018; GTZ, 2003). BRT is "a public mode providing high capacity and consuming cleaner fuels. It also has many comfortable and luxurious facilities with high technology functions for faster and safer travel, including exclusive busway, convenient stations, comfortable articulated buses, and intelligent transportation systems" (Satiennam, Fukuda, & Oshima, 2006, p. 59). BRT is used in an integrated way with specialized vehicles on dedicated bus lanes, it can significantly enhance mobility in the city (Md Rohani et al., 2013). BRT systems are introduced to provide high-quality, modern rapid transit systems to deliver fast, comfortable, economical, and safe mobility to urban dwellers (Chaudhary, 2020).

In 2008, the Lagos State Government, introduced the BRT system of bus services in Lagos State to uplift the conditions of road transportation and make PT attractive (Aminu & Pearse, 2018). The Lagos BRT does not have the advanced features of the TransMilenio in Bogota or the Brisbane South East Subway in Australia both of which are very expensive to complete (Mobereola, 2009). The Lagos BRT scheme is being implemented in phases. For example, LAMATA (2009) said the first phase of the scheme was from Mile 12 to CMS, a 22.5-kilometre corridor, which took off with 220 high-capacity buses (LAMATA, 2009). The Mile 12 - CMS corridor is branded BRT Lite (LAMATA, 2009, 2012, 2016). The second phase is the extension of the BRT lane from Mile 12 to Ikorodu on a stretch of a 13.5 km road with the BRT running in the middle of the road to avoid interference from other road users (LAMATA, 2016). The second phase took off in 2015 with over 400 air-conditioned buses (Bakare, 2016). The Mile 12 - Ikorodu corridor is branded BRT Classic (LAMATA, 2012, 2016). With the approval of Governor Akinwunmi Ambode, the construction of a new BRT corridor along Oshodi to Abule-Egba has commenced under the supervision of LAMATA (Proshare, 2018). The construction is nearing completion and can be described as the third phase of the BRT scheme in the state. The BRT services are operated by Primero Bus Services and regulated by LAMATA (LAMATA, 2016).

Service Quality in PT

According to Doyle (1998), services are not easy to define or classify. Services are economic activities that create value and provide benefits for customers at specific times and places as a result of bringing about a desired change on behalf of the recipient of the services (Lovelock, 1983). A service is an act or benefit that does not result in the customer owning anything (Doyle, 1998). Service is an action or an activity that can be offered by a party to another party, which is intangible and cannot affect any ownership (Kotler & Keller, 2009). Service is an intangible activity performed by one party, the provider of a service, and received by another party, the consumer of the service. Because of the intangibility of a service, its purchase and consumption do not result in ownership by the consumer, who merely feels or experiences the service (Aminu, 2022). The essential characteristic of services is their intangibility (Doyle, 1989). From a review of several publications, it was found that the frequently mentioned services' characteristics are intangibility, inseparability, heterogeneity, and perishability (Zeithaml, Parasuraman, & Berry, 1985). Service firms must offer high service quality to attract and retain customers and this leads us to the concept of service quality.

Service quality is defined from the dimensions of technical quality (what the consumer receives) and functional quality (how the consumer receives the service) (Gronroos, 1982). It is viewed as the sum of customer perceptions of the service experience (Johns, 1992). It is the customers' judgment about the overall of a product or service (Zeithaml, et al., 1985). It is related to customers' perceptions and expectations of services (Lewis & Mitchell, 1990).

Service firms must continuously measure their service quality. However, it is indicated that measuring service quality is difficult due to the intangibility, heterogeneity, inseparability, and perishability of services (Bateson, 1995; Parasuraman et al., 1985; Zeithaml et al., 1985). Despite the difficulty of measuring service quality, Pakdili and Kurtulmusoglu (2014) argued that measuring service quality provides service firms with intelligence that enables them to create a useful database.

The service quality of buses is defined to include attributes such as service coverage, frequency of services, hours of service, and service reliability (Md. Rohani et al., 2013). A recent empirical analysis revealed that the passengers' most important expectations are employees' empathetic approach toward customers, technical specifications of buses, error-free services, and competent employees (Pakdili & Kurtulmusoglu, 2014). Therefore, service quality in PT reflects the commuters' perception of transit performance (Tyrinopoulos & Anthoniou, 2018). Bus operation service quality can be measured based on specific criteria such as accessibility, availability, and reliability (Md. Rohani et al., 2013). However, public buses are characterized by insufficient service, poor bus schedules, the absence of facilities, including bus stops and shelters, and the infrequency of services, leading to the services being intensely compromised (Mashiri et al., cited by Govender, 2014).

In the PT industry, service quality is influential in determining commuter choices (Pakdili & Kurtulmusoglu, 2014). In this regard, commuters, who have the choice to drive their automobiles, may commute in buses if they perceive the buses as consistently delivering high service quality and vice-versa. "The highly competitive market conditions in the passenger transportation industry pressure service firms to adopt an attitude of customer-oriented service quality" (Pakdili & Kurtulmusoglu, 2014, p. 375). Beirao and Cabral (2006) have admonished bus operators, that are less customer-oriented, to become more market-oriented and competitive by providing satisfactory service quality. Therefore, bus operators are under persistent pressure to improve their service performance continuously and to provide evidence of their services meeting commuters' expectations (Sudaryanto & Kartikasari, 2007).

From the foregoing, an improvement in the transit service quality can certainly attract further users (Eboli & Mazzulla, 2007). Pioneer studies on service quality (Berry et al., 1985; Gronroos, 1982; Parasuraman, Berry, & Zeithaml, 1985; Zeithaml et al., 1985) have highlighted the importance of delivering superior service quality to consumers.

Theoretical Model of Service Quality

SERVQUAL is a multi-dimensional construct and model for evaluating customer expectations and perceptions in the service industry (Parasuraman et al., 1988). The authors developed a five-dimensional and 21-item scale for the evaluation of customers' expectations and perception of service quality along these dimensions: tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. These dimensions were found to have a high correlation (Parasuraman et al., 1988). Yarimoglu (2014) noted that with the increasing importance of services, scholars, and practitioners have been operating on the quality of services delivered. Service quality measures the degree to which the service delivered meets the customers' expectations (Yarimoglu, 2014). Empirical studies validating the SERVQUAL dimensions have been conducted in several service sectors including hotel and hospitality (El Saghier, 2015; Johns, 1992), telecommunication (Loke, Taiwo, Mat Salim, & Downe, 2011), retailing (Vandamme & Leunis), banking (Kamila, & Nantel, 2000; Bilgin, & Shemwell, 1997), higher education (Rowley, 1997), and public transport (Cunningham, Young, & Lee, 2000; Eboli & Mazzulla, 2007, 2012; Perez, Abad, Garrillo, & Fernandez, 2007).

Each of the five dimensions of SERVQUAL (Parasuraman et al., 1988) is described below.

1. *Tangibles* relate to the extent to which the appearance of the personnel, equipment, and facility of the service providers is satisfactory and projects an image of high quality.
2. *Reliability* describes the degree to which a service is consistently and dependably delivered by service providers.
3. *Responsiveness* is the degree to which service providers are willing to provide prompt service, help, and assistance to customers.

4. *Assurance* is the extent to which service providers are knowledgeable, courteous, and able to inspire trust and confidence.
5. *Empathy* describes the degree to which the employees of service organizations provide individual and caring service to customers.

Research Methods

The target population for this research work was the commuters of Lagos BRT at both Ikorodu and Agric Bus Terminals in Lagos State. We collected data from a valid sample of 545 commuters of the bus services, who have been riding at least once a week for at least one year. The data was obtained in the peak period of the morning of May 9, 2019, by no fewer than 25 research assistants using both dynamic and static surveys. The dynamic survey was carried out inside the buses as they moved from one terminal to another, while static survey was undertaken in the terminals by administering the questionnaire to the commuters in the queue waiting to board the buses. Before the administration of the questionnaire, a letter of consent was sent to LAMATA, the regulator of the BRT services in the state. We were given consent to collect data from the BRT commuters at both Ikorodu and Agric bus terminals.

Parasuraman et al.'s (1988) SERVEQUAL 22-item scale was adapted to produce an 18-item scale. The reduced number of items was to make the questionnaire attractive to the respondents. Based on the experience of the researchers, the attitude of many Lagosians to surveys is lackadaisical. Tangibles had four items; reliability, four items; responsiveness, three items; assurance, four items; and empathy, three items. The questionnaire also had a section on the respondents' demographics, including personal data, car ownership, and ridership of BRT buses. The 18 items were measured on a five-point Likert scale, 1 to 5. 1 represents Strongly Disagree; 2, Disagree; 3, Undecided; 4, Agree; and 5, Strongly Agree.

The research instrument was pretested on April 26, 2019, with a valid sample of 71 commuters of the Bus Franchise Services (BFS) at Iyana-Ipaja, Alimosho Local Government Area, Lagos State, Nigeria. We used Cronbach's Alpha to test the internal consistency of our scale. The Cronbach coefficients for each of the five dimensions are shown in table 3 below. Multiple regression analysis was used to establish the contribution of each of the five SERVQUAL dimensions to the Lagos BRT service quality.

This paper tested the following hypothesis:

H0: Commuters' perception of Lagos BRT service quality is significantly low.

Results and Discussion

Analysis of Respondents' Demographics and Ownership of Car and Use of BRT

Table 1: Respondents' Demographics

Variables	Percentage	Variables	Percentage	Variables	Percentage
Gender:		Marital status:		Occupation:	
Male	58	Single	29	Civil servant	16
Female	42	Married	47	Private sector	32
Total	100	Separated	22	Self-employed	38
		Widow/Widower	02	Students	14
		Total	100	Total	100
Age bracket:		Educational qualify:			
Below 20 years	08	WASC	20		
21-30 years	36	ND/NCE	38		
31-40 years	32	HND/B.Sc./BA	26		
41-50 years	07	M.Sc./MA/MBA/M.Ed	09		
Above 50 years	07	PhD	02		
Total	100	Total	100		

Source: Author's Computation from Field, 2019.

Our descriptive statistics showed that 58% were male respondents while 42% were female respondents. Therefore, more male respondents participated in the survey. In terms of age distribution, the respondents in the age bracket of 21-30 years constituted the largest group, accounting for 36%; followed by the respondents in the age category of 31-40 years, accounting for 32%; 8% were below 20 years; and 7% for each of the categories of respondents in the age groups of 41-50 years; and 51 years and above. This suggests that the majority of BRT commuters were young. The marital distribution of the respondents showed that 47% were married; 29% were yet to marry; 22% were divorcees; and the rest, 2% were widows and widowers. Therefore, the majority of the respondents were married.

Respondents possessing a minimum qualification of ND/NCE emerged as the largest group with 38%; followed by a group of respondents that possessed a minimum qualification of B. Sc. or its equivalent with 26%; 20% possessed an 'O'Level qualification; 9% possessed M. Sc. and equivalent; and 2% possessed Ph.D. This indicates that the majority of the respondents possessed a minimum qualification of ND/NCE. The majority of the respondents, 38%, reported being self-employed; 32% were private companies' employees; and 16% were civil servants; Students accounted for the rest, 14%. Therefore, the majority of the respondents were self-employed.

Table 2: Respondents' Ownership of Automobiles and Use of BRT

Variables	Percentage	Variables	Percentage	Variables	Percentage
Ownership of automobile:		Period of riding in BRT:	Marital status:	Frequency of boarding BRT	
Yes	55	Less than 1 year	18	Once a week	16
No	45	1-2 years	34	Twice a week	25
Total	100	3-4 years	48	Thrice a week	27
BRT bus terminal		Total	100	Four times a week	10
Ikorodu terminal	59			Everyday	14
Agric terminal	41			Occasionally	06
Total	100			Weekends only	02
				Total	100

Source: Author's Computation from Field, 2019.

With regards to the ownership of automobiles, 55% of the respondents claimed they have a car while 45% didn't own a car. With regards to the length of time, the respondents have been commuting in BRT, 48% have been riding in BRT for a period of 3-4 years (since the Ikorodu-CMS corridors became operational in 2015); 34% have been boarding the buses for a period of 1-2 years; while the rest, 18% have been patronizing the buses for less than 1 year. Twenty-seven percent of the respondents claimed they used to board the buses thrice a week; 25% said they used to board the buses twice a week; 16% said they used to board them just once a week; 14% claimed they used to board them every day; 10% said they used to board them four times a week; 6% admitted they used to occasionally commute in the buses; and the rest, 2% commuted in BRT on weekends only. Finally, a large number of the respondents, 59% boarded the bus at the Ikorodu bus terminal while 41% boarded at the Agric bus terminal. Therefore, there were more respondents at the Ikorodu bus terminal.

Table 3: The scale reliability, factor loading, and Mean

Sub-scales and items	Factor loading	The mean value of individual items
Tangibles (Alpha = .891)		
The staff of BRT is neat and well dressed.		3.01
Lagos BRT has a modern looking bus.	0.685	2.97
BRT terminals are visually appealing.		
BRT bus interior is neat and hygienic.	0.746	3.19
	0.714	2.96
	0.794	2.94
Reliability (Alpha = .683)		
BRT buses always arrive at destinations on time.		2.59
BRT buses don't break down on road frequently.	0.715	2.57
I can easily book a ticket for my journey.		
I don't wait too long before I board a bus.	0.651	2.94
	0.638	2.72
	0.673	2.20
Responsiveness (Alpha = .793)		
BRT staff tell you exactly when buses will arrive.		2.32
BRT staff give you prompt service.	0.682	2.14
BRT staff are always willing to help you.		
	0.747	2.40
	0.623	2.53

Assurance (Alpha = .779)			
BRT staff are polite.			2.63
BRT staff are trustworthy.	0.748		2.64
I feel safe dealing with BRT staff.	0.739		2.60
BRT staff have the support of the management to do their job well		0.752	2.74
		0.703	2.63
empathy (Alpha = .807)			
BRT staff provide individualized services.			2.47
BRT staff understand my needs.	0.607		2.54
BRT staff have my best interest in mind.		0.735	2.49
		0.751	2.46

Source: Author's Computation from Field, 2019.

From the table above, each of the Cronbach alpha values of the five dimensions (.891, .683, .793, .779, and .807) is above the threshold of 0.6 specified by Nunnally (1978), suggesting that all the items in the scale are internally consistent, and therefore, the instrument is, thus reliable. We used an Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) to test the validity of all items in the scale. The oblique factor analysis was conducted as the variables were highly correlated with one another. The results of the Principal Component Analysis (PCA) with Kaiser normalization are shown above. A standardized factor loading greater than .6 shows a relatively high factor loading. The results showed that all items of the five dimensions of service quality of Lagos BRT were valid, with a factor loading over .6. Finally, the means for all the 18 items in the scale, except one, were low, below 3.0, indicating that the service quality dimensions of Lagos BRT are low and less satisfactory to many of the commuters of the buses.

Table 4: ANOVA^b (Goodness of the fit model)						
Model		Sum of Squares	DF	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	91.274	4	22.818	32.758	.000 ^a
	Residual	327.395	470	.697		
	Total	418.669	474			

Predictors: (Constant), Tangibles, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy.

Source: Author's Computation from Fieldt, 2019.

ANOVA tests the ability of a model to significantly predict or explain the expected outcome. The F-ratio in table 4 tested the extent to which the overall regression model is a good fit for the data. The results showed that at least one of the five dimensions in the model statistically significantly explained service quality in BRT, i.e. $F(4, 95) = 32.758, p < .0005$, indicating that the model is a good fit.

Table 5: Regression Results for Lagos BRT Service Quality.

Variables	Standardised Beta	t	Sig.
Constant	1.684	11.685	.247
Tangibles	.117	4.072	.000
Reliability	.384	5.054	.000
Responsiveness	.365	3.592	.000
Assurance	.249	6.724	.000
Empathy	.033	.632	.527

Source: Author's Computation from Field, 2019.

In testing the study's single hypothesis, we used the value of standardized beta () and t-test statistics level of significance (Sig.) for each of the five dimensions of Lagos BRT service quality in the co-efficients table above. As a rule, where $p < .05$, we accept the hypothesis because it is statistically significant, otherwise, we reject it. The four of the SERVQUAL five dimensions in the model are statistically significant, i.e. (= .384, $p < .05$) for reliability; (= .365, $p < .05$) for responsiveness; (= .249, $p < .05$) for assurance; and (= .117, $p < .05$) for tangibles. Empathy (= .033, $p > .05$) is not statistically significant. Therefore, we accepted the hypothesis that: Commuters' perception of Lagos BRT service quality is significantly low.

The unreliability of BRT services and the non-responsiveness of BRT personnel to commuters' plights contributed largely to the perceived low service quality of Lagos BRT. For example, most of the passengers perceived BRT services as not reliable. It has been reported that the number of BRT buses plying the BRT bus corridors has considerably reduced from 434 to 250 (Proshare, 2018), causing commuters to suffer under the long waiting time to board buses at Ikorodu and other terminals in Lagos metropolis (Adeyeye, 2018). Also, most of the commuters perceived the personnel of BRT buses as non-responsive to their needs and problems. For example, it is reported that commuters feel that BRT personnel are indifferent to their plight when they seek information from them (Igomu, 2018).

Conclusion and Recommendations

The paper evaluated the perception of service quality of Lagos BRT, using the five dimensions specified in Parasuraman et al.'s SERVQUAL model - tangible, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. The results of the multiple regression

analysis conducted showed that four of the five dimensions of the SERVQUAL scale - tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, and assurance were statistically significant, while the last one, empathy, was statistically insignificant. We, therefore, concluded that the commuters of Lagos BRT perceived the service quality of the buses as significantly low.

Based on the conclusion of this paper, the following recommendations are made. One, the bus operators, Primerio Bus Services, should provide additional buses to increase the number of buses servicing the mammoth crowd of passengers patronizing BRT, from Ikorodu and its environs, daily. This will reduce the passengers' long waiting times at terminals and improve their positive perception of responsiveness and empathy. Second, the company should provide regular customer care training and workshop for all the categories of employees of BRT services. This will enhance their capacity to provide prompt service, help and assist passengers, and improve passengers' positive experiences. Three, they should ensure continuous maintenance of buses and facilities (bus shelters and bus stops) and payment of adequate remuneration to staff to enable them to look neat and presentable. This will provide tangible evidence about the quality of services passengers should expect. Four, they should undertake a regular passenger satisfaction survey to track passengers' perception of service quality and how passengers evaluate service quality. It has been suggested that for successful management of service quality, marketers need to understand how customers evaluate their services (Cunningham, Young, & Lee, 2000). Furthermore, the regulator, LAMATA, should scale up its regulatory roles to prevent a delivery gap in the bus services. Finally, ensuring a high-service quality PT in the Lagos metropolis will help achieve a sustainable transport system in the most populated city in Africa.

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